

THE VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH TEMPERATURE

BY RAM GOPAL

A study of the variation of specific conductivity, μ with temperature, t in concentrated aqueous solutions, both above and below the saturation temperature, shows that while $\mu-t$ curves for viscous solutions have a positive curvature and obey the Kohlrausch's equation viz., $\mu_t = \mu_0(1 + \alpha t + \beta t^2)$, those for solutions of low viscosity are almost straight lines and obey the equation of Walden viz. $\mu_t = \mu_0(1 + \alpha t)$.

The behaviour of the latter is in contradiction with Heim's observations on a number of supersaturated aqueous solutions and as the study in this paper is confined to such solutions, an explanation, depending upon the ionic hydration hypothesis and the concept of depolymerisation of water molecular complexes, is suggested to account for this anomaly.

The variation of specific conductivity with temperature has been studied by a number of workers specially by Gotrain, Arrhenius, Deguisne and others. From the observations of Deguisne (Dissertation, Strassburg, 1893), Kohlrausch (*Sitz. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1901, 42, 1026) suggested that the variation of μ with temperature t , in very dilute solutions ($N/100$ and $N/1000$) of HCl, K_2SO_4 , $BaCl_2$, KOH, KCl, KNO_3 , $Ba(NO_3)_2$, $NaNO_3$, and Na acetate etc., can be represented by

$$\mu_t = \mu_0(1 + \alpha t + \beta t^2) \dots \quad (1)$$

Heim (*Ann. Physik*, 1886, 27, 643) showed this equation to hold in a number of solutions, both above and below the temperature of saturation. Bousefield and Lowery (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1903, 71, 42), Kunz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 42, 591) demonstrated that the equation (1) held only within a certain range of temperatures and beyond this range $\mu-t$ curves did not follow the course predicted by this equation and approached the temperature axis asymptotically. Hence any conclusion arrived at below this range on the basis of the equation would lead to erroneous conclusions (cf. Prakash, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 907; Musharan and Prakash, *ibid.*, 1946, 50, 251).

Walden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 73, 257) from his study of this problem in non-aqueous media down to very low temperatures (in some cases as low as -100°) found that most of his results above zero degree could be expressed by a simple linear equation,

$$\mu_t = \mu_0(1 + \alpha t) \dots \quad (2)$$

Worshoven (*ibid.*, 1890, 5, 581) found equation (2) applicable to some of the concentrated solutions of cadmium salts.

In connection with some work on supersaturation, specific conductivity of a number of highly concentrated and supersaturated aqueous solutions was studied and that offered an opportunity to examine the applicability of these equations and also to ascertain whether Heim's conclusions are so general as to admit applicability of the equation of Kohlrausch to all the supersaturated solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The measurement of conductivity was carried out in the usual way using a cell having a high cell constant, similar to that of Jones and Bickford (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 604) and made of pyrex glass and of about 10 c.c. capacity in order to avoid the use of a large amount of chemicals. Although, in general, five concentrations were studied, μ values corresponding to only one concentration have been shown in Table I to economise space. From the data $\mu-t$ curves have been plotted and some typical ones are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

TABLE I
Specific conductivity (μ) at different temperatures.

Substance.	Concn. * (Sw 100)	$\mu \times 10^3$ at						
		30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.	60°.
KCl	38.7	43.68	46.57	49.46	52.52	55.60	58.40	—
KBr	73.5	47.49	50.28	53.08	56.10	58.98	61.97	—
KNO ₃	54.01	28.20	30.25	32.48	34.61	36.52	38.80	—
KIO ₃	11.60	4.380	4.790	5.190	5.62	6.02	6.441	—
KClO ₃	12.29	9.335	10.13	10.86	11.70	12.42	13.20	—
NaNO ₃	102.5	21.27	23.54	25.69	27.89	30.20	32.56	34.95
NaClO ₃	118.0	17.32	19.05	20.29	22.86	24.89	26.97	—
NH ₄ Cl	43.8	—	57.38	60.67	63.90	67.31	70.98	—
NH ₄ NO ₃	270.0	34.02	36.31	38.57	41.18	43.68	46.31	—
KCN	286.0	—	24.02	26.41	28.37	30.72	32.56	34.52
Na acetate	59.96	7.295	8.410	9.781	11.08	12.52	13.90	—
K acetate	250.0	4.602	5.560	6.382	7.465	8.58	9.724	10.78
K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	44.38	27.85	29.84	32.20	34.11	36.70	38.69	—
(NH ₄) ₂ C ₂ O ₄	9.52	9.664	10.62	11.35	12.20	13.06	13.94	—
K ₂ SO ₄	14.01	12.78	14.02	14.90	15.04	16.02	17.65	—
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	80.04	29.43	31.94	34.31	36.84	39.40	41.75	—
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	21.69	12.98	13.68	15.15	16.10	17.18	18.21	—
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	12.70	5.690	6.238	6.810	7.445	8.039	8.648	—
BaCl ₂	40.70	20.87	22.40	24.02	25.71	27.41	29.12	—
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	69.83	10.23	12.27	12.39	13.51	14.62	15.68	16.86
CuSO ₄	33.48	6.367	7.562	8.271	8.948	9.724	10.37	11.12
MgSO ₄	45.78	3.602	4.020	4.583	5.162	5.790	6.369	—
H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	17.66	13.47	14.01	14.69	15.35	15.81	16.42	16.89
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	33.60	22.68	24.45	26.14	27.89	29.74	31.28	—

* Concentration is expressed in grams of solute in 100 g. of water.

DISCUSSION

From the Figs. 1 and 2 it appears that except for oxalic acid, the curves fall into two distinct categories. To the first category in which the curves are almost linear,

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

belong most of the solutions with low viscosity e.g., solutions of KCl, KBr, KNO₃, NH₄Cl, etc. In such solutions therefore the equation (2) of Walden will hold at least within the temperature range studied here. Obviously in these cases $\partial\mu/\partial t$ is a constant.

In the second category, μ - t curves are not linear but have more or less a positive curvature (Fig. 2). The solutions have comparatively a high viscosity than those of the first category. This class includes the solutions of NaNO₃, NaClO₃, KCNS, Na and K acetates, MgSO₄, etc. In general, higher the viscosity, greater the curvature, i.e. greater the value of the temperature coefficient $\partial\mu/\partial t$. In these cases the equation (1) of Kohlrausch will be applicable. It is therefore the substances of the second category which behave similarly to those examined by Heim. To the substances of the first category Heim's conclusions will not be applicable.

As the range of applicability of these equations is very much limited, no useful purpose will be served by a further detailed study of these equations. However, an explanation is evidently desirable to account for the anomalous behaviour of the solutions of the first category as, according to Kohlrausch and others, dilute aqueous solutions obey the quadratic law in numerous cases at ordinary temperatures and according to Heim, concentrated and supersaturated solutions are also governed by the same rule.

According to Jone and Jacobson (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1908, 40, 555), departure from the straight line nature of the μ - t curves is due to the lowering of the hydration of ions as a result of rise in temperature. This lowering in hydration increases the mobility of ions, over and above that due to increase in kinetic energy as a result of the rise in temperature, and this lowering will be greater, the higher the temperature. Then the μ - t curves will naturally assume a positive curvature. Besides, the depolymerisation of water molecular complexes, resulting in a lowering in viscosity, which will be greater, the higher the temperature, will add to this effect and in all dilute solutions therefore the curves will have their $\partial\mu/\partial t$ positive. It appears very probable that the observations of Deguise and others in dilute solutions are mostly due to depolymerisation of water molecular complexes at higher temperatures.

When an electrolyte is dissolved in water, it is well known that it causes a depolymerisation of water molecular complexes and it may eventually change most of them into simple H₂O molecules at very high concentrations. At lower concentrations all the ions are individually hydrated to the maximum, depending upon their attraction for H₂O molecules and also majority of water molecular complexes will be present excepting a few which have been depolymerised due to the effect of the solute. This will result in a rise of specific conductivity with temperature in the manner discussed above.

As the concentration is further raised, more depolymerisation of water molecular complexes occurs and hydration of individual ions goes on diminishing. If an ion in question has a very small tendency for hydration e.g., K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺, NO₃⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, and Cl⁻ etc., a stage will be reached at a sufficiently high concentration, when nearly all the water complexes will be depolymerised, and also hydration of individual ions will be almost negligible. Such solutions will have a very low viscosity inspite of high concentration. Hence, rise in the value of specific conductivity with temperature in these cases will be, in the main, solely due to the increase in the kinetic energy of the almost unhydrated ions. Hence curves would be linear in these cases as is borne out

by experiments. It is very likely that if the temperature is very much lowered, some slight curvature in μ - t curves may be found, as at lower temperatures hydration will play a more important role.

However, if the ions concerned have a great affinity for water molecules, the environments will be quite different. Although water molecular complexes will be slowly depolymerized, these will be replaced by heavily hydrated ions as the concentration rises. Due to high hydration, the lowering in the hydration of individual ions, as a result of the rise in concentration, will not affect the outcome much, and the majority of the water molecules will be bound up with the solute ions in some way or other. Hence, as has been discussed above, μ - t curves have a positive curvature and they obey a quadratic law.

The μ - t curves for oxalic acid do not belong to any of the two categories mentioned in the foregoing pages, and have a negative curvature (Fig. 2). Although μ still increases with t , $\partial\mu/\partial t$ is negative. This phenomenon has been studied by Watson and Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, 46, 368), Usanovitch (*Compt. rend. U. S. S. R.*, 1939, 25, 608) and others. Probably this phenomenon is closely connected with the low degree of dissociation of the acid and decreasing dielectric constant of the medium with rising temperature which will still lower the degree of dissociation of the acid (cf. Davies, "Conductivity of Solutions", 1930, p. 126).

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